

BUILDING EMPOWERED STUDENTS: THE ROLE OF PRIDE, SELF-ACTUALIZATION, AND TRANSCENDENCE IN ENHANCING INSTITUTIONAL LOYALTY

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of pride and social narcissism on students' self-actualization and self-transcendence within the framework of customer citizenship behavior. A quantitative methodology was employed, surveying 391 students from three universities associated with LPTNU in East Java, Indonesia. The data were analysed using SEM Amos. The results revealed that pride significantly and positively influenced self-actualization, self-transcendence, and customer citizenship behavior, whereas social narcissism was found to affect only self-actualization. The findings of this research align with the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), as positive attitude, social norms, and perceived self-control were important factors in shaping the students' behaviours. For managerial implications, this might involve a student development program based on institutional identity, achievement awards, and social activities to strengthen the loyalty toward the institution. This research offers an important contribution to higher education marketing strategies that are supportive of individual development but at the same time strengthen institutional image.

Keywords: Actualization, Citizenship, Narcissism, Pride, Transcendence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, organizations faced increasing competition and were consequently developing closer ties with the workforce and considering customers an asset to be leveraged towards the achievement of better performance. This paradigm shift fostered greater attention to customers' contacts and opinions viewed as a source of continuous improvement. Feedback from either employees or customers is one of the basic mechanisms for organizational learning and improving performance. When put into practice, it leads to better quality of products and services, thus leading to loyalty and a closer relationship with the customers (Bettencourt, 1997; Groth, 2005).

Customer feedback becomes important in sites such as annual Indonesia Customer Experience Champions, awarding companies that innovate in meeting customer expectations. This initiative highlights the essential role of customer-centric innovation in cultivating loyal customers who voluntarily contribute to the company's growth. One such is Customer Citizenship Behaviour, which can be termed as the voluntary and constructive actions of customers to help a company enhance its service quality without expecting explicit rewards in return. According to Groth (2005) and Bove et al. (2009), despite the fact that CCB has the potentials to reduce operational costs and improve service delivery, it has not been fully researched within diverse cultural and service environments.

Previous research grounded in the Theory of Reasoned Action and the Theory of Planned Behavior has demonstrated that customer behaviours often voluntary are more likely to emerge when the individuals perceive such actions as meaningful, socially endorsed, and within their control (Hwang et al., 2020; Hossain et al., 2023). However, these have largely focused on specific industries and cultural contexts, which renders the understanding of these behaviours across diverse contexts incomplete. Although pride, which is a self-conscious emotion derived from achievement, has been said to lead to self-actualization and then subsequently toward CCB, the intervening roles of self-transcendence and social narcissism within this process are not well considered so far (Maslow, 1970).

Self-transcendence-a movement toward maturity and the interdependence between individuals in their social milieu-and social narcissism-characterized by the need to be recognized on social networks-operate together to form interesting dimensions through which customer motivation is understood. Both constructs provide insight into the shifting dynamics of customer engagement in the digital age, when people have increasing opportunities to express themselves and their values in their relationships with companies (Yi et al., 2011; Hwang et al., 2020). Although relevant, the existing literature has failed to provide insights on how these psychological drivers shape CCB, especially in the higher education sector-a domain where service quality and customer satisfaction hold strategic importance.

The present study, therefore, tries to fill these gaps by incorporating TRA and TPB with constructs of pride, self-actualization, self-transcendence, and social narcissism in order to investigate their combined impact on CCB. This research specifically investigates students from three universities under Lembaga Pendidikan Tinggi Nahdlatul Ulama (LPTNU) in East Java, Indonesia, which offer a different educational environment that blends religious and academic values. This setting provides a new context in which to examine how cultural and institutional characteristics interact with customer behaviour theories.

This research offers multiple significant contributions to the current body of literature in terms of expanding its scope by applying it within a different service context. First, it provides a first evidence of the relevant role that psychological drivers such as pride and social narcissism play regarding CCB promotion. After that, it explores for the very first time the intervening role that self-transcendence and self-actualization play for a deeper insight into engagement mechanisms. Finally, this study indicates that customers are considered an integral part of value creation, where customer involvement represents a strategic issue. Thus, from a practical viewpoint, these results provide recommendations for improvement regarding service quality and competitive advantages for educational institutions.

Thus, this study fills the literature gap by developing both theoretical and strategic frameworks that give organizations the ability to develop and maintain customer loyalty through voluntary value-driven behaviours.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

By consumers posting on social media their pride and empathy regarding the services and products that they have experienced, this can effectively increase the loyalty intentions of these

consumers and other consumers to create trust in consumers (He et al., 2022). Likewise, consumers have a sense of pride and mindfulness for the product as a whole and have public self-awareness so that consumers will be satisfied, where consumers will then behave voluntarily to show the public about the products they have experienced (Hwang & Lee, 2019). The results of the study Hwang et al. (2020), show a positive association between pride and self-actualization. With the consumer's sense of pride in the products or services received from the company, it will make the consumer want to show their potential or abilities (Self-Actualization) and the desire to provide more information if it is needed by others (self-transcendence). The connection to the Theory of Reasoned Action and the Theory of Planned Behavior, as proposed by Ajzen & Fishbein (1988), it can be explained that pride influences an individual's attitude towards certain behaviours and can also increase and strengthen Perceived Behavioural Control. If individuals feel proud of their identity or achievements (e.g., academic achievement or social contribution), the individual will be more inclined to possess an optimistic outlook and feel capable and controlled in efforts to achieve self-actualization so that individuals are more likely to develop stronger intentions in useful social activities.

From the previous description, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H1: Pride has a significant effect on Self-Actualization in University students in PLTNU East Java.

H2: Pride has a significant effect on Self-Transcendence in University students in PLTNU East Java.

Narcissism according to John (2012), is an approach to others that is self-centred and self-concerned. Usually narcissistic behaviour is unaware of one's actual state and how others view it. This ignorance causes adjustment problems for them. Narcissists are very self-centred, always emphasize that they are perfect (self-congratulatory), and view their desires and hopes as important. Baumeister & Vohs (2001) self-esteem, which has been demonstrated to maintain a stable and affirmative correlation with narcissism, constitutes a significant element of narcissism and is intricately linked to subjective well-being and psychological health. Social narcissism encompasses beneficial aspects of the self that derive from self-reflection and self-awareness, as noted by Hwang et al. (2020), and is associated with personal development, as indicated by Sovine (1999), ultimately facilitating self-actualization. Furthermore, Hwang et al. (2020) identified a positive association between social narcissism and both self-actualization and self-transcendence, particularly in the context of purchasing fair trade coffee. Narcissistic individuals often prioritize the symbolic significance of a product or service over its practical utility when attempting to impress and earn admiration from others (Sedikides et al., 2013). Based on this observation, a hypothesis can be derived:

H3: Social Narcissism has a significant effect on Self-Actualization in University students in PLTNU East Java.

H4: Social Narcissism has a significant influence on Self-Transcendence in University students in PLTNU East Java.

Self-transcendence is characterized as an altruistic value and motivation, wherein individuals strive to attain goals that extend beyond their personal interests. According to Hwang et al. (2020), self-transcendence promotes self-actualization and encourages individuals to engage with the world beyond their own experiences. Reischer et al. (2021) contend that the attitudes associated with self-actualization and the formation of profound relationships with others exemplify the compassionate essence of self-transcendence. Hwang et al. (2020) contend that self-transcendence enables individuals to engage in acts of service towards others, thereby exceeding the level of Self-Actualization within Maslow's hierarchy. Based on this assertion, a corresponding hypothesis can be developed:

H5: Self-Actualization has a significant effect on Self-Transcendence in University students in PLTNU East Java.

The value-driven behaviour model emphasizes that values, typically viewed as influences on attitudes and actions, serve as the primary motivations for behaviour. Self-actualization and self-transcendence are identified as key motivations influencing consumer consumption. When consumers' personal values align with the values offered by a service, they experience satisfaction with that service. Research by Zhang & Bloemer (2008) indicates that value congruence, which is assessed through consumers' perceptions of the alignment between the values of a service brand and their own personal values, significantly impacts consumer loyalty and the likelihood of positive word-of-mouth communication. Customer Citizenship Behaviour (CCB) refers to voluntary actions and individual choices made by customers that are neither directly anticipated nor explicitly rewarded. However, these behaviours collectively contribute to enhanced service quality and facilitate the efficient operation of the organization (Groth, 2005). Therefore, after consumers perceive that the service they have received from a company or organization is in accordance with their values and abilities, the consumer will feel satisfied and the consumer will be called to be able to inform others even without being asked by the company or organization. From the previous description, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H6: Self-Actualization has a significant effect on customer citizenship behaviour in students of universities in PLTNU East Java.

H7: Self-Transcendence has a significant effect on customer citizenship behaviour in students of universities in PLTNU East Java.

Customers exhibiting high levels of involvement tend to focus more on the specifics of the service and demonstrate a greater interest in the services provided, so that customers feel capable (Self-Actualization) and have more ability (Self-Transcendence) to convey details of the services they have received, where customers know more in advance, so that customers behave voluntarily to convey information related to the services they have received to new/other customers and also behave voluntarily in providing feedback to the company. This study extends its scope by examining the relationship between customer engagement, self-actualization, self-transcendence, and Customer Citizenship Behaviour (CCB). Customer Citizenship Behaviour (CCB) can affect increased revenue and can create competitive

advantage. Where in Bettencourt (1997) research, Customer Citizenship Behaviour (CCB) is a positive impact of customer satisfaction, because he believes customers will appreciate a better experience and increase personal satisfaction and the company's goodwill, which will encourage them to do good. Hwang et al. (2020), the findings of his research indicate that interactions between customers are influenced by their familiarity with the services and the reputation of the facilities. Consequently, these customer-to-customer interactions have a substantial impact on customer citizenship behaviour (CCB). Furthermore, by involving consumers in the service activities of a company or organization which is a system for incorporating external feedback and consumer insights into the innovation process (Cui & Wu, 2016), so that this can be a source of strategic data to gain competitive advantage. According to Melander (2020) that customer involvement is a very important method, especially in providing input for product development in the industrial market. With the above description, the following hypotheses can be formulated:

H8: Customer involvement moderates the effect of Self-Actualization on customer citizenship behaviour in students at PLTNU East Java University.

H9: Customer involvement moderates the effect of Self-Transcendence on customer citizenship behaviour in students at PLTNU East Java University.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

2. METHODS

This research is an explanatory casual study; it uses a quantitative methodology through a survey technique to explain the casual relationships among variables. Data collection was done by questionnaire, and then SEM Amos, version 29, was used to analyse the data in order to test the model of the relationship between constructs. The study population included 16,881 students from three universities under LPTNU East Java, namely the Islamic University of

Malang, the University of NU Surabaya, and the University of NU Sidoarjo, which received the advanced category based on the Internal and External Quality Assurance System. Respondents were active undergraduate students (semesters 1–8) who actively used social media. A sample of 391 respondents was determined using the Slovin formula and the Proportional Random Sampling technique. This technique ensures random and proportional sampling in each population strata, so that the research results represent the relationship between variables more comprehensively. Comprehensive information regarding the sample utilized in this study is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Collected Sample

University	Population	Total Sample
Islamic University of Malang (UNISMA)	10.831	251
NU University of Surabaya (UNUSA)	4.178	97
NU University of Sidoarjo (UNUSIDA)	1.872	43
Total	16.881	391

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

3. RESULTS

Respondent Profile

Based on the research results, the first indication to discuss the findings is to discuss the results of the respondent profile as shown in the table below.

Table 2: Respondent Demographic Profile

Respondent profile	Description	Freq	Percentage
University	UNISMA	251	64.2
	UNUSA	97	24.8
	UNUSIDA	43	11.0
Gender	Male	111	28.4
	Female	280	71.6
Social Media Used	Facebook	2	0.5
	Instagram	13	3.3
	Instagram, Tiktok	1	0.3
	WhatsApp	92	23.5
	WhatsApp, Facebook	1	0.3
	WhatsApp, Instagram	61	15.6
	WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook	16	4.1
	WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, Tiktok	100	25.6
	WhatsApp, Instagram, Tiktok	103	26.3
	WhatsApp, Tiktok	2	0.5
Social Media Usage Details	Using WhatsApp	375	95.9
	Using Instagram	293	74.9
	Using Facebook	119	30.4
	Using Tiktok	206	52.7
Total Respondents		391	100.0

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

From the table above, most respondents are from UNISMA (64.2%) and female (71.6%). The most used social media is WhatsApp (95.9%), followed by Instagram (74.9%), and Tiktok (52.7%), while Facebook is only used by 30.4%. The combination of WhatsApp, Instagram, and Tiktok is the most dominant (26.3%), while single use of WhatsApp reaches 23.5%. Respondents who use all four-social media, namely WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, and Tiktok, as many as 25.6%, show a high preference for WhatsApp as the main communication media.

Construct Validity

Construct validity assesses how effectively a test measures a specific construct. In Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), the evaluation of construct validity is performed through convergent validity. A common guideline indicates that a construct is considered to achieve convergent validity if the indicator associated with it has a standardized regression weight (factor loading/lambda) of no less than 0.50, with a more desirable threshold of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 3: Construct Validity Test

Construct	Indicator	Factor Loadings/ Lambda (CFA)
<i>Pride (X1)</i>	X1.1	0,753
	X1.2	0,889
	X1.3	0,718
<i>Social Narcissism (X2)</i>	X2.1	0,505
	X2.2	0,848
	X2.3	0,918
<i>Self-Actualization (Z1)</i>	Z1.1	0,748
	Z1.2	0,839
	Z1.3	0,878
<i>Self- Transcendence(Z2)</i>	Z2.1	0,781
	Z2.2	0,814
	Z2.3	0,860
	Z2.4	0,809
<i>Customer Involvement (Z3)</i>	Z3.1	0,716
	Z3.2	0,847
	Z3.3	0,785
	Z3.4	0,847
	Z3.5	0,787
<i>Customer Citizenship Behavior (Y)</i>	Y.1	0,857
	Y.2	0,858
	Y.3	0,722
	Y.4	0,626
	Y.5	0,668

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

The findings from the assessment of construct validity are presented in Table 3. This table indicates that within the measurement model, every indicator yields a factor loading value (lambda) exceeding 0.50. Consequently, these indicators are deemed valid for constructing the

factors of pride, social narcissism, self-actualization, self-transcendence, customer involvement, and customer citizenship behaviour, thereby satisfying the criteria for convergent validity.

Construct Reliability

The assessment of construct reliability is conducted through the evaluation of the construct reliability value. A construct is considered reliable when this value exceeds 0.70 (Solimun et al., 2017). Additionally, Hair et al. (2017) noted that while a construct reliability value should ideally be above 0.70, a value greater than 0.60 may still be deemed acceptable, provided that each indicator has satisfied the criteria for convergent validity. The findings from the construct reliability assessment for each construct are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Construct Reliability Test

Variable	Construct Reliability	AVE
Pride (X1)	0,832	0,624
Social Narcissism (X2)	0,813	0,606
Self-Actualization (Z1)	0,863	0,678
Self-Transcendence (Z2)	0,889	0,667
Customer Involvement (Z3)	0,897	0,637
Customer Citizenship Behavior (Y)	0,865	0,566
Rule of thumb	$\geq 0,70$	$\geq 0,50$

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Table 4 indicates that every variable yields a construct reliability value exceeding 0.70, along with an AVE value surpassing 0.50. Therefore, it can be inferred that the indicators assessing the constructs of pride, social narcissism, self-actualization, self-transcendence, customer involvement, and customer citizenship behavior are deemed reliable.

Direct Effect Analysis

The initial phase of hypothesis testing involves assessing the direct effect, which entails evaluating the significance of the direct influence pathway. This process examines the estimated parameters that characterize the relationship between variables corresponding to each theoretical hypothesis. A hypothesis may be accepted if the path parameters demonstrate statistical significance in the predicted direction of influence. Specifically, for a positive direction, the path parameters should exceed zero, while for a negative direction, they should fall below zero (Hair et al., 2017). In the assessment of direct effects, hypothesis testing is employed to evaluate the significance of the direct relationship between variables, utilizing the critical ratio (CR) and the probability value (p-value). The determination of the significance of this direct influence is based on the criterion that if the CR value is greater than or equal to 1.96 or the p-value is less than or equal to the nominal level of 5%, it is concluded that a significant influence exists. Conversely, if the CR value is less than 1.96 or the p-value exceeds the nominal level of 5%, it is concluded that the influence is not significant. The subsequent findings pertain to the examination of structural relationships conducted to evaluate each research hypothesis, as derived from the SEM output.

Table 5: Testing Structural Relationships between Variables

No	Direct Influence Path	Std. Estimate	S.E. bootstrap	C.R.	P-value	Hypothesis Decision
1	X1 → Z1	0,438	0,051	7,588	0,007	H1 accepted
2	X1 → Z2	0,201	0,076	2,618	0,006	H2 accepted
3	X2 → Z1	0,286	0,083	3,361	0,016	H3 accepted
4	X2 → Z2	0,052	0,070	0,814	0,343	H4 rejected
5	Z1 → Z2	0,599	0,089	7,562	0,012	H5 accepted
6	Z1 → Y	0,281	0,147	2,544	0,034	H6 accepted
7	Z2 → Y	0,393	0,128	3,641	0,008	H7 accepted

Note:
X1: Pride, Z2: Self-Transcendence
X2: Social Narcissism, Z3: Customer involvement
Z1: Self-Actualization, Y: Customer Citizenship Behavior
(*) S.E., C.R., and p-value calculated using the bootstrap bias-corrected percentile method

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Indirect Effect Analysis

The subsequent phase of hypothesis testing involves assessing the significance of the indirect influence pathway, commonly referred to as testing for indirect effects. In Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), this assessment is performed utilizing the bias-corrected percentile method, which represents an advancement of the Sobel Test tailored for the SEM framework. The process of hypothesis testing to determine the significance of the mediation effect follows a similar approach, employing the critical ratio (CR) value alongside the probability value (p-value). The determination of significant influence between variables is based on the criterion that if the CR value is equal to or greater than 1.96, or if the p-value is less than or equal to the established significance level of 5%, it is concluded that a significant influence exists. The subsequent findings pertain to the examination of the indirect impact of pride and social narcissism on customer citizenship behavior, facilitated by the mediating roles of self-actualization and self-transcendence.

Table 6: Indirect Effect Analysis

No	Indirect Path	Specific Indirect Effect (Bias-corrected percentile method)		
		Std Estimate	P-value	Remark
1	X1 → Z1 → Y	0,123	0,002	Significant mediation
2	X2 → Z1 → Y	0,080	0,034	Significant mediation
3	X1 → Z2 → Y	0,079	0,028	Significant mediation
4	X2 → Z2 → Y	0,020	0,678	Mediation is not significant

Note: X1: Pride, Z2: Self-Transcendence
X2: Social Narcissism, Z3: Customer involvement
Z1: Self-Actualization, Y: Customer Citizenship Behavior
(a) p-value calculated using the bootstrap bias-corrected percentile method approach

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Total Effect Analysis

The findings from the analysis regarding the overall impact of pride, social narcissism, self-actualization, and self-transcendence on customer citizenship behavior among university students at LPTNU East Java are displayed in Table 7.

Table 7: Total Effect Analysis

No	Total effect on customer citizenship behavior (Y)	Total Effect	C.R	P-value	Rank
1	Pride (X1)	0,202	2,827	0,010	3
2	Social Narcissism (X2)	0,101	1,983	0,048	4
3	Self-Actualization (Z1)	0,281	6,032	0,005	2
4	Self-Transcendence (Z2)	0,393	6,853	0,003	1

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

The findings from the total effect analysis indicate that the variables of pride, social narcissism, self-actualization, and self-transcendence collectively exert a significant influence on customer citizenship behavior, as evidenced by a p-value of less than 0.05. The total effect coefficient represents the aggregate of both the direct and indirect effects. Additionally, the total effect value is illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Total Effect Analysis

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Figure 2 shows that self-actualization in university students in LPTNU in East Java is more driven by pride, then social narcissism, while self-transcendence in students is more driven by self-actualization, then pride and social narcissism. Furthermore, customer citizenship behaviour in students is more driven by self-transcendence, below that is self-actualization, pride, and finally social narcissism. The results of the total effect analysis can also provide information on the priority scale in efforts to strengthen citizenship behaviour in university students in LPTNU East Java, from the highest priority to the lowest priority.

Moderating Effect Analysis

In this research, the examination of the moderating effect will employ a two-stage methodology, as the objective of the analysis is to assess the significance of the moderation effect (Hair et al., 2017). Additionally, the analysis of the moderation effect can be enhanced through Multigroup Analysis (MGA), also referred to as the conditional effect, which is instrumental in identifying variations in the strength of influence among variables across different levels of competency. The conditional effect test uses the procedure proposed by Hayes (2017) to validate the occurrence of the moderating effect.

Table 8: Moderating Effect Analysis

Moderating relationship	Std. Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P-value	Hypothesis Decision
Customer involvement moderates the influence of self-actualization on customer citizenship behavior $Z1*Z3 \rightarrow Y$	0,876	0,168	2,869	0,030	H8 accepted
Customer involvement moderates the influence of self-transcendence on customer citizenship behavior $Z2*Z3 \rightarrow Y$	0,216	0,123	1,545	0,160	H9 rejected

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Table 8 presents the findings regarding the moderating effect of customer involvement on the relationship between self-actualization and customer citizenship behavior. The results indicate a significant influence, evidenced by a CR value of 2.869, which exceeds the threshold of 1.96, and a significance value (p-value) of 0.030, which is below the alpha level of 5%. The moderation effect coefficient is recorded at 0.876, indicating a positive relationship, so it is concluded that customer involvement strengthens the influence of self-actualization on customer citizenship behaviour in university students in LPTNU East Java. Students with high involvement, the influence of their self-actualization in encouraging increased citizenship behaviour will be stronger. Table 8 presents the findings regarding the moderating effect of customer involvement on the relationship between self-transcendence and customer citizenship behavior.

The results indicate an insignificant influence, as evidenced by a CR value of 1.545, which is below the threshold of 1.96, and a significance value (p-value) of 0.160, exceeding the α level of 5%. Furthermore, the coefficient for the moderation effect is recorded at a mere 0.216, so it is concluded that customer involvement does not moderate the effect of self-transcendence on customer citizenship behaviour in university students in LPTNU in East Java. Students with high involvement, the effect of their self-transcendence in encouraging increased citizenship behaviour will not change.

Table 8 presents the findings regarding the moderating role of customer involvement on the relationship between self-transcendence and customer citizenship behavior. The results indicate an insignificant effect, as evidenced by a CR value of 1.545, which is below the

threshold of 1.96, and a significance value (p-value) of 0.160, exceeding the alpha level of 5%. The coefficient for the moderation effect is recorded at a mere 0.216, so it is concluded that customer involvement does not moderate the effect of self-transcendence on customer citizenship behaviour in university students in LPTNU East Java. Students with high involvement, the effect of their self-transcendence in encouraging increased citizenship behaviour will not change.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings of this present study show that pride is in actualization. Students who are proud of the university they attend are more motivated to actualize themselves, not only in terms of academics but also in every sphere of life. This fact agrees with the study conducted by Hwang et al. (2020) that found pride positively influences self-actualization. Furthermore, pride increases the self-confidence of students, which is very important in venturing into other interests and talents, facing new challenges optimistically.

Apart from self-actualization, pride also has an extended influence on self-transcendence. Students proud of their university would transcend personal interests to greater contributions within the community. For instance, they would become more active ambassadors of their institution via social networks or by personally participating in community activities. It also proves the Theory of Reasoned Action and Theory of Planned Behaviour that pride fuels positive attitudes toward social behaviour, self-transcendence.

There was a significant relationship between social narcissism and self-actualization, proving that the higher the student has a degree of social narcissism, the more concern and attention to their personal recognition and achievement are, which all eventually contribute to self-development. While the effect of social narcissism on self-transcendence was not significant. That would mean that the more outwardly directed variant of narcissism does not facilitate the transcendence of personal interests in contributing selflessly to society. This finding runs counter to the findings of Bushman & Baumeister (1998), who found a possible positive relationship between social narcissism and social contribution.

The effect of self-actualization on self-transcendence is significant, reflecting a linear relationship where students who have achieved personal self-development are more likely to focus on larger social goals. This is supported by Maslow (1970), which places self-transcendence as the highest stage in the hierarchy of human needs. Students who have achieved self-actualization show greater sensitivity to the needs of others, motivating them to engage in positive contributions to their community.

The present study shows that self-actualization and self-transcendence have a significant effect on each aspect of customer citizenship behaviour. In other words, the more a student can attain self-development or go beyond their own interests, the more active an advocate they will be for their university. For instance, they will recommend the university to other prospective students, thus contributing to the development of the institution with positive feedback. This reflects the validation of the TRA and TPB that positive attitudes encourage proactive

behaviour that supports the organization. Therefore, it proves that customer involvement was significant to moderate the correlation of self-actualization with the constructs of customer citizenship behaviour. The involvement constructs further strengths the impact of self-actualization on campus citizenship among students. While on other hands, engagement as a mediator, did not stand out significantly with self-transcendence vs. customer citizenship behaviour. These findings call for ensuring provision of a facilitative campus environment towards achieving student engagement leading to constructive attitude deictic towards higher educational institution ends.

These results thus present important lessons through which universities can use pride and other psychological elements as means to support student development. The research also confirms the complementarities of the two concepts: self-actualization and self-transcendence, in shaping appropriate behaviour in students. As such, the results can be adopted in developing appropriate self-development and social activity programs that universities can utilize in fostering self-actualization and self-transcendence in their students in order to create a well-engaged and motivated set of students.

This study validates the TRA and TPB and offers theoretical support and practical implications for higher education marketing strategies. For instance, universities could promote either alumni success or social contribution opportunities as a means to attract new students.

Managerial Implication

These findings can be utilized by university management to nurture the pride of students through institutional identity programs, achievement awards, and social contributions. The personal development of students, by including soft skills training and community service in the curriculum, can foster self-actualization and self-transcendence. Furthermore, students should be encouraged to participate in various campus activities in order to strengthen their emotional attachment towards the institution for CCBs that are supportive of the image of the university in a sustainable way.

5. CONCLUSION

This study has underlined the critical role of psychological elements such as pride and social narcissism in shaping students toward self-actualization, self-transcendence, and its impact on CCB. Indeed, pride played an important role in the intention of the students to develop to their fullest potential and transcend beyond self-interest for social contribution. However, social narcissism only supported self-actualization and was not significant in influencing self-transcendence. The interventions aimed at involving students more deeply may further enhance the connection between self-actualization and institution-oriented attitudes. This research confirms the Theory of Reasoned Action and the Theory of Planned Behaviour by showing that positive attitude, social norm, and perceived self-control contribute significantly to account for the behaviour of students. By integrating such findings into university student management strategies, a setting that supports individual growth while strengthening the overall image of the institution can be established.

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